

Descriptions of supplementary codes and data

Pneumatic elastostatics of multi-functional inflatable lattices: Realization of extreme specific stiffness with active modulation and deployability

The Matlab code file `E1_inflatable` presents the variation in non-dimensionalized elastic moduli $E1/E$ of hexagonal lattices with non-dimensionalized internal pressure p/E . It generates data for the Equation 24 of the paper which is then used to plot the Figure 5(A-D). Each subplot in Figure 5, i.e., Figure 5 (A-D) considers different combinations of cell configurations (i.e., different values of cell angle θ) for a particular value of h/l .

The Matlab code file `E1_inflatable_rl` presents the variation in non-dimensionalized elastic moduli $E1/E$ of hexagonal lattices with non-dimensionalized internal pressure p/E . It generates data for the Equation 24 of the paper by considering different values of ratio of radius and length, i.e., r/l , which is then used to plot the Figure 5(E-F). The Figure 5(E-F) considers a particular value of h/l and cell angle θ .

The data set generated in the file `E1.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 5A and the data set generated in the file `E1_rl.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 5F.

The Matlab code file `E2_inflatable` presents the variation in non-dimensionalized elastic moduli $E2/E$ of hexagonal lattices with non-dimensionalized internal pressure p/E . It generates data for the Equation 32 of the paper which is then used to plot the Figure 6(A-D). Each subplot in Figure 6, i.e., Figure 6 (A-D) considers different combinations of cell configurations (i.e., different values of cell angle θ) for a particular value of h/l .

The Matlab code file `E2_inflatable_rl` presents the variation in non-dimensionalized elastic moduli $E2/E$ of hexagonal lattices with non-dimensionalized internal pressure p/E . It generates data for the Equation 32 of the paper by considering different values of ratio of radius and length, i.e., r/l , which is then used to plot the Figure 6(E-F). The Figure 6(E-F) considers a particular value of h/l and cell angle θ .

The data set generated in the file `E2.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 6B and the data set generated in the file `E2_rl.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 6E.

The Matlab code file `G12_inflatable` presents the variation in non-dimensionalized elastic moduli $G12/E$ of hexagonal lattices with non-dimensionalised internal pressure p/E . It generates data for the Equation 53 of the paper which is then used to plot the Figure 7(A-D). Each subplot in Figure 7, i.e., Figure 7 (A-D) considers different combinations of cell configurations (i.e., different values of cell angle θ) for a particular value of h/l .

The Matlab code file `G12_inflatable_rl` presents the variation in non-dimensionalized elastic moduli $G12/E$ of hexagonal lattices with non-dimensionalized internal pressure p/E . It generates data for the Equation 53 of the paper by considering different values of ratio of radius and length, i.e., r/l , which is then used to plot the Figure 7(E-F). The Figure 7(E-F) considers a particular value of h/l and cell angle θ .

The data set generated in the file `G12.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 7C and the data set generated in the file `G12_rl.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 7E.

The Matlab code files `E1_inflatable_reldensity` and `G12_inflatable_reldensity` present the variation of the ratio of the elastic moduli and relative density with internal pressure, (as shown

in Figure 8 of the paper), at different values of r/l along with the variation of t/l ratio, with the assumption of thin honeycomb cell walls ($t/l \sim 10^{-5}$). The Figure shows that the specific properties of the inflatable structures are quite high and the stiffness by weight ratio for inflatable beams can increase up to a thousand times when compared with that of solid circular beams. The Matlab code `E1_inflatable_reldensity` is used to plot the Figure 8 (A-B) and the Matlab code `G12_inflatable_reldensity` is used to plot the Figure 8 (C-D) by considering different values of ratio of radius and length, i.e., r/l for a particular value of t/l . The results are presented in non-dimensional forms considering $(E1/\rho) / (E1/\rho)_s$, $(E2/\rho) / (E2/\rho)_s$ and $(G12/\rho) / (G12/\rho)_s$ for the elastic moduli and p/E for the internal pressure. In the Figure, the subscript s denotes the properties that correspond to that of a solid circular beam.

The data set generated in the file `E1_reldensity.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 8A and the data set generated in the file `G12_reldensity.xlsx` corresponds to Figure 8D.